

EDITOInfra

European Digital Twin Ocean

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Data Lake – User Guide and API

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1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the document

To describe how the data lake will be built, how it fits in the EDITO infrastructure and how it can be used by the Copernicus Marine Service and EMODnet teams to add data, and by twin builders to develop their twins. This document will describe the user interactions available to efficiently use data inside the EDITO Data Lake. These features will be explained without going into too many details as they will keep evolving until the end of the project.

1.1 EDITO-Infra general context

In the document, **EDITO** refers to the **European Digital Twin of the Ocean** web platform (up and running, accessible with a web browser). **EDITO-Infra** refers to the project or to the code base repository implementing the web platform. The EDITO platform is then one deployed instance of the code developed in the context of the EDITO-Infra project.

The European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EDITO) comprises two main parts: "EU Public Infrastructure backbone for the European Digital Twin of the Ocean" (EDITO-Infra) and "European Digital Twin of the Ocean Underlying Models" (EDITO-Model Lab). EDITO-Infra aims to establish the EU Public Infrastructure backbone by integrating key components from existing EU ocean programs like "Copernicus Marine Service" and "EMODnet" into a unified digital framework. It serves as both the project name and the code base, the platform is named EDITO, forming the basis for ongoing EU Digital Twin of the Ocean development. The EDITO platform will host applications from various projects, supporting the implementation of advanced ocean models, including those from the EDITO-Model-Lab and Mission Lighthouses projects.

The ongoing evolution of marine data portals is guided by two fundamental objectives. The primary aim is to enhance the efficiency of scientists' work and simultaneously reduce associated costs. This necessitates tackling the escalating challenge posed by the expansion of dataset sizes and heightened data resolution. Strategies to address this challenge include implementing measures to limit data transfers. Moreover, recognizing the divergence between computer protocols and networks from the field of earth science, there is a focus on simplifying access to High-Performance Computing (HPC). The proposed solution for this objective involves the strategic implementation of effective data subsets and the integration of near-data computing capabilities.

The second core objective is centered on fostering contributions to the field of ocean science. This entails a twofold approach: improving the FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) of both data and associated processes. Additionally, there is a concerted effort to broaden participation, encouraging the engagement of diverse stakeholders beyond traditionally identified institutes. The proposed solution for this objective envisions the provision of efficient tools within an open and collaborative platform.

At the nexus of these pivotal objectives lies the European Digital Twin of the Ocean—an overarching initiative poised to redefine how marine data is managed and utilized for scientific advancements. Serving as a unifying force, this initiative is set to harmonize disparate elements, fostering a comprehensive ecosystem that propels ocean science into a new era characterized by accessibility, efficiency, and collaboration.

To fulfill this need, the EDITO platform is decomposed into three main components: the EDITO-Infra Data Lake, the EDITO-Infra Engine, and the EDITO-Infra Service. The general technical architecture of the three components is described in the D2.2 EDITO-Infra architecture – blueprint, domain, stack, and deployment https://mercatoroceanfr.sharepoint.com/sites/EDITO-InfraExternal/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc={6F63021A-7653-4405-8872-986BA1688127}&file=D2.2_EDITO-Infra_architecture_-_blueprint,_domain,_stack_and_deployment.docx&action=default&mobileredirect=true document. However, this document focuses on the understanding of the mechanisms that fill the feature at the core of a Digital Twin of the Ocean, that is to enable the browsing and access of any ocean data seamlessly with adaptive resolution. This feature is implemented by the EDITO-Infra Data Lake and relies on the EDITO-Infra Engine for on-demand calculations.

1.2 Definition table

ARCO: analysis-ready and cloud-optimized data refers to data that has been processed, cleaned, and formatted to meet the requirements of analytical tools or processes as well as structured or stored in a way that takes advantage of cloud computing capabilities for storage, processing, and scalability.

CF Conventions: The Climate and Forecast conventions define metadata that provide a definitive description of what the data in each variable represents, and the spatial and temporal properties of the data. This enables users of data from various sources to decide which quantities are comparable, and facilitates building applications with powerful extraction, regridding, and display capabilities.

CF standard name table: The Climate and Forecast standard name table (part of the CF Conventions), defines strings that identify physical quantities and variables.

Copernicus Marine Toolbox. It is a free and easy-to-use tool that interoperates with the Copernicus Marine Data Store with the aim of covering any use case, from retrieval of metadata to a complete dataset, or just a sub-part, for any type of product: numerical models, satellite and/or in-situ observations.

Data Lake: a Data Lake is a repository of raw or refined data, structured or not, without format constraints, as opposed to a data warehouse, which is a repository of highly structured and refined data. Data lakes leverage the development of high-speed and scalable Cloud based storage solutions (object, file, and block storages).

EDITO Data Lake: The "data access" component of the EDITO platform, composed of the EDITO Data Storage and the EDITO Data Catalog.

EDITO STAC implementation: This is the method chosen to organize our STAC catalogs, collections, and items for this project.

NetCDF: Network Common Data Form is a standardized file format used for storing multidimensional scientific datasets. It is commonly employed in various scientific fields like geosciences, meteorology, and oceanography due to its capacity to manage complex data structures efficiently.

OGC: OGC stands for the Open Geospatial Consortium. It is an international consortium that develops and publishes open standards for geospatial information and technologies. The OGC is focused on promoting interoperability and collaboration in geospatial data and services.

OGC API – Features: A multi-part standard that offers the capability to create, modify, and query spatial data on the Web and specifies requirements and recommendations for APIs that want to follow a standard way of sharing feature data.

Resto: An open-source metadata catalog and a search engine dedicated to geospatialized data.

STAC: The SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) specification provides a common structure for describing and cataloging spatiotemporal assets. A spatiotemporal asset is any file that represents information about the earth captured in a certain space and time.

STAC Catalog: A simple, flexible JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) file of links that provides a structure to organize and browse STAC Items.

STAC Collection: A STAC object extending the STAC Catalog object with additional information such as the extents, license, keywords, providers, etc. that describe STAC Items that fall within the Collection.

STAC Item: The core atomic unit, representing a single spatiotemporal asset as a GeoJSON feature plus datetime and links.

WMS: Web Map Service is a standard protocol for serving georeferenced map images over the internet. It allows users to access and retrieve map images from a server and overlay them onto their own maps or applications.

Zarr: A data storage format for multi-dimensional arrays, optimized for efficient handling of large datasets in scientific computing. It supports compression, chunking, and is commonly used in Python for tasks involving arrays and data analysis.

2. EDITO-Infra Data Lake

2.1 Design criteria and technical overview

The EDITO Data Lake is designed to fulfill two main requirements:

1. A great experience to let end-users easily search, retrieve, and add data, by enforcing a metadata framework that ensures standardized and meaningful categorization of information
2. An efficient retrieval of the data, optimized for both cloud and edge computing

More details on EDITO-Infra whole design criteria and technical overview are available in [D2.2 "EDITO-Infra architecture – blueprint, domain, stack and deployment"](#) document.

2.1.1 The EDITO-Infra Catalog

2.1.1.1 *Share data from various location and sources*

A pivotal aspect of our data lake design is the creation of a unified catalog amalgamating diverse datasets from various locations and sources. This criterion goal is to encourage inclusivity and set the stage for a comprehensive understanding of the oceanic environment. This approach fosters a collaborative framework, where researchers can access and analyze data from different regions, enriching the overall quality and scope of oceanographic insights. This diverse data integration enables a holistic representation of the oceanic environment, capturing the complexity of interactions among different aspects of the marine environment, like physical, chemical, biological, geological properties and information on human activities.

A second aspect is the continuous enlargement of this data, with the updating of the existing one as well as the addition of new ones. The goal of the platform is to be as complete as possible for users to easily find the data needed and just as easily be able to contribute to it with groundbreaking scientific information.

2.1.1.2 Public and Private Inclusivity

A defining feature of our catalog is its commitment to accommodate both public and private datasets within the same framework. Publicly accessible data fosters collaboration, while the incorporation of private datasets ensures the protection of proprietary information, striking a delicate balance between openness and confidentiality.

2.1.1.3 Technical overview

To solve [requirement number 1](#) several solutions have been implemented. One is to harmonize access to already existing ocean data portals (such as Copernicus Marine Service and EMODnet). This is done by using a standard and metadata format, flexible enough and enforcing a common metadata scheme using oceanographic conventions. The main goal here is to let the end-users search data without having to know the underlying technical aspect behind it. The process used to provide the user with these huge datasets directly into EDITO is described into [3.EDITO Data Lake base content](#).

To propose a comprehensive catalog to users, a technical choice was needed to find a technology to easily retrieve assets, this was made possible thanks to the dynamic classification and semantic search available in the resto software. Resto is an open-source tool providing a dynamic catalog using the STAC standard and implementing OGC features API.

STAC (SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog) is an open standard for cataloging geospatial assets in a machine-readable format. The STAC specification is designed to provide a common framework for organizing and describing satellite imagery, remote sensing data, and other geospatial datasets. The catalog organizes information about the assets in a structured and flexible manner, making it easier to discover, access, and share geospatial data.

A STAC implementation is organized in two main ways, first is the STAC Collections and STAC Items which allow to register all elements into a complete database. If it were for a shop, its collections and items would index all existing references. The second organization is the creation of multiple catalogs. These catalogs will refer to existing catalogs, collections, and items to create a new structure. For a shop it could be the edition of a season catalog containing specific goods and organized to better answer this season's needs.

2.1.1.3.1 EDITO STAC structure

Figure 1 EDITO STAC structure

In our case the STAC collections and STAC items will meet the same purpose to refer to all existing data, and there will be multiple STAC catalogs allowing different organizations. There will be a root STAC catalog created as a first proposition, but every user will be able to create their own specific data organization, share them or make them public and accessible to everyone.

The EDITO STAC implementation is structured as follows:

1. One STAC catalog “Variable families” that aggregates the variables from the STAC collections into different sub catalogs such as “Chlorophyl” or “Temperature”.
2. STAC collections, which correspond to scientific variables, referred to by their CF standard name when possible.
3. STAC items, within a STAC collection, where each item is a piece of homogeneous data (the variable over its dimensions).

Thanks to STAC as well as the OGC Features and standard-based extensions, advanced search and access are available through the EDITO catalog. Users can find data by location, areas, keywords, or content.

2.1.1.3.2 Centralized catalog

EDITOInfra

Figure 2 Centralized catalog referencing the Copernicus Marine catalogue and EMODnet. The possibility to reference other sources of data is represented by the icon of different servers connected to EDITO catalogue.

The EDITO catalog has been built to reference data available at any location to harmonize data access to various sources. Figure 2 shows that a different approach has been used for referencing Copernicus Marine and EMODnet data, due to the different solutions adopted by these two services. Copernicus Marine data are available and hosted on the same cloud as EDITO and made available by the Copernicus Marine Data Store in native format (netCDF) and ARCO. They are referenced in the EDITO catalogue but are not copied in EDITO storage. EMODnet data instead are available only in native format (netCDF, Shapefile, ...) and are transformed in ARCO by a tool running on EDITO. In order to avoid performance issues and for providing fast and easy access to the users, they are not only referenced but also stored in the EDITO catalog, in native and ARCO format.

In the same way, users will be able to either add data to the EDITO Data Lake storage and reference it into a catalog or directly create catalogs referencing external data, if the EDITO standard and catalog structure are being respected.

2.1.1.3.3 Asset materialization

Figure 3 Asset materialization

Furthermore, the whole architecture has been constructed so that the catalogue is referencing also all the data that can be generated by tools and models available on EDITO. This implies that if users are requesting this data, they are generated on demand. As explained in the [D5.1 Engine – User Guide and API](#) document the engine is composed of processes that produce data. These processes will be implementing the OGC Processes standard, so that they are defined by the output data they will produce. That way if a process can produce data, the catalog will be able to index it. If a user wants to access it, then it will be generated on the go thanks to the engine.

2.1.2 The EDITO-Infra Data storage

2.1.2.1 Public and Private Inclusivity

Data storage within our comprehensive system provides users with the flexibility to store actual data, offering a customizable approach based on individual needs. Users can choose to integrate their data into organized catalogs for broader accessibility. This data can either stay private and the user will be able to add it to private catalogs, or the data may be transferred and shared in the public storage to be available to all users. EDITO will define and agree with the EU commission a governance process for managing the new data generated by or made available on EDITO.

2.1.2.2 Technical overview

To respond to [requirement number 2](#) The Amazon S3 (Simple Storage Service) technology, selected, offers a scalable and highly available cloud storage solution well suited for geospatial data. S3's architecture allows for optimized storage and retrieval of Analysis-Ready Cloud-Optimized (ARCO) data and metadata, enabling seamless analysis and processing of geospatial information in the cloud environment, enhancing accessibility, performance, and cost-effectiveness for data-intensive tasks.

Private and public S3 storage are available in two separate parts of the platform to ensure the users' content privacy. However, to encourage collaboration the presence of a simple action to simplify the sharing and the transfer of data between different spaces is needed.

A data orchestrator allows to automate workflows and in our case its goal is to harvest the user personal data in three ways:

1. To help the user's data become public by having access to automatic data ingestion, automatic check and test of the data, and automatic format conversion.
2. To help the user create its own private STAC catalog by creating automatic metadata reference
3. If the user has a private STAC catalog, to help make it public with automatic metadata ingestion, and check and test of the metadata.

This data orchestrator has already been planned and will be implemented in the next phase of the project

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Figure 4 EDITO-Infra data orchestration

2.2 EDITO Data Lake user experience

2.2.2 User interface

Different user interfaces have been put into place to answer the multiple interactions needed to create, add, delete and update data or catalog.

2.1.2.1 The EDITO platform home

Figure 5 EDITO platform home page

The home page of the EDITO platform is a web page displaying at the bottom the platform three main components:

1. The tutorial web page to learn about the platform content and how to contribute to it.
2. The Datalab web page where the user will be able to discover the services, processes and log in to its personal workspace (storage, credentials, running services and running processes)
3. The viewer to browse the EDITO catalog and to display its content.

The header of all the platform web pages contains links to:

1. the home page,
2. the three main components tutorials, DataLab, and viewer,
3. the common website of both EDITO-Infra and EDITO-Model Lab
4. the email address of the EDITO platform support.

2.1.2.2 The EDITO tutorials

Figure 6 EDITO Tutorials page

The "[Courses and Tutorials](#)" page on our platform provides a comprehensive repository of educational content for users to navigate and learn about the platform's functionalities. Each tutorial is tagged with relevant keywords, allowing users to easily categorize and identify content based on their interests or specific needs.

Tutorials linked to specific services can directly trigger the launch of those corresponding services from within the tutorial interface. This direct launch capability is designed to reduce friction between learning theoretical concepts and applying them in a practical environment.

Access to the page is unrestricted, requiring no separate login for viewing the tutorials.

To contribute to the content, users follow a streamlined process using GitLab's merge request mechanism. Contributors can make changes, propose new tutorials, or enhance existing ones.

For example, one of the tutorials is on Data Storage Principles, featuring MinIO, an object storage system compatible with Amazon's S3 API. Accessible from any location, MinIO allows direct file access within Datalab's data science services, enhancing analysis reproducibility. The tutorial covers file management, sharing, and usage, providing insights into creating directories, uploading files, and sharing public links.

2.1.2.3 The EDITO viewer

Figure 7 EDITO viewer

The Data [Viewer](#) is a robust tool for geospatial data exploration, organized in a structured spatiotemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) tree format. With dynamic map visualization in both 2D and 3D, users can seamlessly switch perspectives for a comprehensive analysis. The viewer supports temporal and spatial filters, enabling focused exploration based on time intervals or user-defined Areas of Interest. Additionally, the viewer seamlessly integrates with Web Map Service (WMS), allowing users to display WMS tiles.

2.1.2.4 The EDITO DataLab

The [DataLab](#) website is a platform tailored for efficient data management and service deployment.

1. The "My Account" section facilitates access and configuration of essential account information. Users can manage various aspects, including configuring usernames, managing email settings, handling passwords, and directly connecting personal access tokens to services.
2. "My Files" offers access to S3 Buckets, allowing users to navigate and manage files efficiently. This section provides instructions for file exploration within S3 Buckets and details on uploading and downloading files.
3. The "Service Catalog" serves as a central hub for exploration, launch, and configuration of services. Within this section, users can leverage a smart viewer for streamlined data visualization, access development tools, and utilize processing and analysis tools for efficient data handling.
4. "My Services" provides a comprehensive list of currently running services. Users can monitor these services. Inside any of these services users can be automatically connected to their personal data present in the "My files" section.
5. Processes will be available with the same kind of accessibility as the services. By default, the data produced by processes will be directly stored inside the user personal data "My Files".
6. In the "My Secrets" section, users can define variables that will be accessible in services in the form of environment variables. This involves securely defining variables and seamlessly integrating these secrets into services for enhanced security and configuration management. It can also be used to seamlessly access external S3 storage, or other data authenticated locations.

Here the main user interface concerning the DataLab is the "My Files" section which corresponds to users personal S3 storage. It directly allows data upload and download as well as providing the capacity to organize data by using a hierarchy of folders.

2.1.3 The EDITO Data Lake Features

The main user experience features of the EDITO Data Lake are the user capacity to:

1. Search data
2. Retrieve data
3. Publish data

These features will be accessible either in a programmatic way or via a user interface.

2.1.3.1 Search data

Efficient and targeted data discovery lies at the core of EDITO's capabilities, providing users with two distinct yet complementary methods to explore and find geospatial information, the STAC and OGC features API and the viewer. The search feature is completely public and available without any authentications.

2.2.3.1.1 STAC and OGC Features API

The first approach involves leveraging the power of our OGC API, adhering to both the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) API standard and the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) standard. This offers a programmatically driven, standardized method for users who require fine-grained control over their queries. This integration enhances the API's capabilities, providing a standardized approach for discovering and accessing spatiotemporal assets. Users can query geospatial data using STAC-compliant requests, ensuring compatibility with a broader ecosystem of geospatial tools and services. For enhanced searching and interoperability, the OGC API Features is also implemented. By leveraging standardized queries, such as filters and expressions, OGC API Features enables more precise and semantically rich searches for geospatial data. These API expose RESTful endpoints that clients can interact with using HTTP methods (e.g., GET, POST, etc.) and support CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations.

2.2.3.1.2 Viewer

For users preferring a more user-friendly and interactive experience, our second approach involves a sophisticated User Interface (UI) that allows exploration based on variable families' catalogs, following the Climate and Forecast (CF) convention, or directly from collections of variables. This ensures a seamless and visually intuitive means for users to browse for geospatial data without the need for extensive technical expertise. This approach enhances the precision and relevance of the search feature by organizing data based on variable families and adhering to established conventions. This search feature complements the browsing action of the user thanks to the semantic search provided by the OGC Features.

Figure 8 Search and retrieve data on EDITO

2.1.3.2 Retrieve data

EDITO offers robust data retrieval mechanisms, allowing users to seamlessly access geospatial information based on their preferences and technical requirements. Whether through a programmatically driven approach using the OGC API adhering to STAC standards or a user-friendly interface, users can efficiently retrieve geospatial data to meet their specific needs.

The retrieve feature is accessibility depends on the data privacy. Data inside the public catalog will be accessible through the designated endpoints, and the system serving the data will be the one enforcing or not its own authentications. Personal data is only available to people the owner chooses to share it with and if they do so.

2.1.3.2.1 STAC and OGC Features API

Upon successful search queries using the OGC API, the retrieved data can be efficiently obtained through standard HTTP methods. The API responses, conforming to the OGC API standard and optionally the STAC format, ensure a consistent and interoperable structure. Lots of scientific development libraries used to process data are compliant with the standard implemented in EDITO-Infra such as STAC, Zarr, CF, etc., and allow users to keep using their preferred tools and language.

2.2.3.2.2 Viewer

Figure 9 Sea surface temperature in EDITO viewer

In the user interface, users can interactively retrieve data by selecting specific items. These items are either found from the search results or directly accessed via the browsing section. It is then possible to choose between different data services to download the data from. If the data has an endpoint serving WMS, this format can be directly displayed in the map view by selecting the item WMS layer.

2.1.3.3 Publish data

Figure 10 Publish data on EDITO

EDITO offers users the possibility to publish their geospatial data. Whether leveraging the simplicity of an S3 API for straightforward data uploads or embracing the standards of STAC/OGC API for broader interoperability, users can effortlessly share and disseminate their datasets.

To publish data be it private or public ones, users will need to be authenticated.

2.2.3.3.1 S3, STAC/OGC Features API

Users can take advantage of Amazon S3 API for efficient and scalable geospatial data publishing. The process involves straightforward uploading to S3 buckets, with secure access controls and metadata inclusion for enhanced discoverability.

The application supports publishing through STAC/OGC Features API, offering a standardized method for data dissemination. Users can create collections, products, and catalogs, adhering to STAC standards, facilitating compatibility with diverse geospatial tools.

2.2.3.3.2 DataLab

The “My Files” page of the DataLab offers access to personal S3 Buckets, allowing users to navigate and manage files seamlessly. This page provides instructions for file exploration within S3 Buckets and details on uploading and downloading files.

3 EDITO Data Lake base content

Figure 11 EDITO Data Lake base content

Directly available inside the EDITO Data Lake will be the Copernicus Marine data and the EMODnet data.

The catalogue has been designed to be easy to access also for users, regardless of their background and their level of knowledge of these marine data. As explained into EDITO STAC structure (2.1.1.3.1), the content will be organized by variable, e.g., sea temperature rather than following the organization by product/dataset or thematic lot/data/product as it is respectively in Copernicus Marine and EMODnet catalogue

However, the STAC standard allowing for multiple catalogs referencing the same data, the Copernicus Marine and EMODnet organizations will also be available as alternatives catalog from the main EDITO one.

3.1 Copernicus Marine

3.1.1 Copernicus Marine Data Store

The Marine Data Store collects all data generated by Copernicus producers for storing and delivering them via standard interfaces.

Copernicus Marine Service data is organized in products and each product is composed of one or more datasets. At present the number of the product is 286, associated to 1081 datasets. The products cover the global ocean and at higher details the Arctic Sea and the regional European seas and provide information for the blue, the green and the white ocean generated by observations in situ and from satellite and by ocean assimilative models producing reanalysis and forecasts. The catalogue is regularly updated with a frequency that depends on the characteristics of the product and can vary from a few minutes to more than one day.

Since November 2023, the marine data store is using a scalable cloud infrastructure which guarantees seamless retrieval of large datasets, high-performance data latency, full metadata access and efficient post-processing features. This implies new functionalities for transforming the original data in netCDF format in ARCO (analysis-ready cloud optimized) format. This process is happening in steps and will end in March 2024 with the cloud optimized access to all the data. Since November 2023 all the gridded products, L4, (68% of the product on the catalogue) are available as ZARR format, an Analysis-ready Cloud Optimized format for storing large N dimensional typed arrays. This format is adapted to the storage of geo-spatial data. To raise the efficiency depending on the kind of access, the data has been chunked in two ways: one enabling easy access by asking for data at a specific date and time and a second one enabling easy access at a specific geographic location. Any viewer of geospatial data needs to have both kinds of access to efficiently visualize data at a certain date all over the world as well as be able to visualize a specific region at any date and time. The second step will be implemented by the end of March 2024 and will allow for the ARCO transformation of all the sparse data (in-situ and satellite along track L3). The ARCO format chosen for these data, after some tests is SQLITE because ZARR is not performing well for non-gridded data.

Since the Copernicus Marine Data Store and EDITO are hosted on the same cloud provider, CloudFerro, EDITO can easily access, transform and add data without duplicating the Copernicus Marine data store. This makes EDITO very efficient and explains why there is no need to store the Copernicus Marine Data in EDITO data lake (see Figure 11).

3.1.2 Copernicus Marine Catalog in EDITO

The Copernicus Marine catalog is organized by product/dataset. The EDITO catalog organization is not meant to be the same, as it was determined that a variable-based organization would be more efficient for the users.

3.1.3 Process for Copernicus Marine data to be available in EDITO Catalog

3.1.3.1 STAC and structure transformation

By using the Copernicus Marine Toolbox, Copernicus Marine data was accessed, and all available metadata was processed to prepare it for integration into the EDITO catalog.

The Copernicus Marine toolbox is a free and easy-to-use tool that interoperates with the Copernicus Marine Data Store with the aim of covering any use case, from retrieval of metadata to a complete dataset, or just a sub-part, for any type of product: numerical models, satellite and/or in-situ observations.

This transformation is twofold:

- Structure the data into a static STAC catalog with collection and items, each scientific variable corresponds to a collection containing homogeneous data as items.
- Creating the variable families organization by cataloguing each variable into its corresponding family to be able to find the data by thematic instead of product/dataset as they are organized in Copernicus Marine catalog.

3.1.3.2 *Ingestion to dynamic STAC catalog*

Once this new STAC structure is completed the ingestion process takes place, for uploading the information into the public EDITO catalog. This step is done using an open-source tool dedicated to harvest static STAC catalog into the dynamic one used for EDITO. This tool adds to the catalog, the metadata reorganized so to match EDITO catalog structure. This is done via a dedicated API for adding the information and their link.

3.1.3.3 *Platform scheduling*

As the Copernicus Marine catalog is continuously updated, this entire process is automatically executed to keep the EDITO catalog up to date. Container images were created for both processes: the STAC static transformation and the ingestion into the EDITO catalog. These images are being executed successively inside a unique scheduler to match the needed frequency. The entire process is launched and executed on the platform.

3.1.4 **Status of Copernicus Marine data availability**

We systematically explore the comprehensive contents of the Copernicus Marine Data Store, ensuring that its metadata undergo regular updates within the EDITO catalog. Specifically, we selectively reference data that strictly adheres to the CF conventions. There could be exceptions due to standards not yet available for specific variables and this will require dedicated discussion and eventually solutions. This approach ensures that the catalog remains up-to-date, and exclusively includes data compliant with the specified conventions for seamless integration and utilization. However, as no automatic verifications are being implemented, most of the data is present, but some may still be absent, and adding an automatic process would be interesting.

3.2 **EMODnet**

3.2.1 **EMODnet Storage**

The EMODnet data is generated by very different consortia of institutes that are organized thematically: biology, physics, bathymetry, chemistry, human activities, geology, seabed habitats.

The EMODnet data is organized and stored in different ways depending on its processing status and data type. The EMODnet data can be in files, databases, shape files. While the EMODNET data products are mostly in raster, NetCDF (network Common Data Form) files and on ERDAP servers.

The list of datasets is maintained in a database (MetaGIS) that drives the map viewer in the portal

3.2.2 **EMODnet Catalog in EDITO**

The EMODnet data products will be referenced in the EDITO catalogue and copied to the EDITO storage. They are transformed to ARCO formats in EDITO, as much as possible, and copied to the S3 storage of the EDITO data lake. This work happens in collaboration with the different scientific communities, and only in as much as possible given the strict timeline and budget.

3.2.3 **Process for EMODnet data to be available in EDITO Catalog**

At the start of the EDITO project, none of the data was available in analysis ready, cloud optimized formats (ARCO). Scripts and data pipelines are written to generate the metadata entries in the EDITO Catalog and to generate the ARCO formats required for the DTO uses.

Selection process: Not all data is meaningful in an ARCO format, some parameters refer to quality of the product, or regional datasets are combined, some older datasets are kept as archive. A selection of the datasets that are meaningful in the data lake is being compiled in collaboration with the different thematic groups.

STAC catalog: additional standardization and mapping to common vocabulary standards are required because the EDITO data lake is organized into parameters rather than datasets. Standards such as climate and forecast (CF) parameters, Darwin Core, WoRMS, EUNIS are used,

The EMODnet data products will adhere to the same principles and structure as the Copernicus Marine catalog described in 2.3.3.1 and create a homogenous catalog that will be ingested and constructed using the same processes also described in 2.3.3.1.

ARCO data: The selected data products are transformed to Zarr if a raster format is applicable and meaningful or to Parquet if a vector format is more appropriate

3.2.4 Status of EMODnet data availability

The different steps in the data generation process (selection, stac generation, arco generation) are all moving in parallel and split between the different thematic groups, so the figures here under are only a snapshot.

Datasets visible in the EMODnet central portal: more than 500.m Transformed to ARCO: Approximately 60 datasets have been selected from all the thematic lots to begin the conversion process.

Described in STAC: More than 50 parameters have been included from these datasets and almost 200 STAC items have been described from this portion of EMODnet datasets.

In the planning for conversion: The conversion of around 400 data products alongside thematic groups is under consideration. The remaining datasets will be converted based on the data products collaboratively deemed necessary for inclusion in the Data Lake in ARCO format. The rest of these data products will be integrated into the central STAC catalog using the same parameter-based structure and processes employed for the initial 50 parameters.

Will not be converted because obsolete/ not fit for purpose / reorganized: Depending on what each thematic group intends to include, there are approximately 60 or more data products that are either obsolete, updated, or unfit for inclusion.